

Attention-Driven AI Model Generalization for Workload Forecasting in the Compute Continuum

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ABSTRACT Effective resource management in edge-cloud networks demands precise forecasting of diverse workload resource usage. Due to the fluctuating nature of user demands, prediction models must have strong generalization abilities, ensuring high performance amidst sudden traffic changes or unfamiliar patterns. Existing approaches often struggle with handling long-term dependencies and the diversity of temporal patterns. This paper introduces OmniFORE (Framework for Optimization of Resource forecasts in Edge-cloud networks), which integrates attention-based time-series models with temporal clustering to enhance generalization and predict diverse workloads efficiently in volatile settings. By training on carefully selected subsets from extensive datasets, OmniFORE captures both short-term stability and long-term shifts in resource usage patterns. Experiments show that OmniFORE outperforms state-of-the-art methods in prediction accuracy, inference speed, and generalization to unseen data, particularly in scenarios with dynamic workload changes and varying trace variance. These improvements enable more efficient resource management in the compute continuum.

INDEX TERMS Attention mechanisms, deep learning, edge-cloud computing, resource optimization, temporal clustering, time-series transformers, workload prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

DESPITE significant strides in cloud computing [1], optimizing resource utilization in edge-cloud networks remains challenging due to the ever-changing nature of cloud-native workloads [2]. Recently, workload prediction has become crucial for service orchestration and resource management in edge-cloud networks [3]. Accurate workload prediction facilitates the proactive and efficient allocation of computational resources based on real-time requirements, minimizing both over-provisioning and under-provisioning [4]–[6]. However, achieving precise workload predictions is complex due to factors such as changes in user demand and workload migrations [7], leading to discrepancies between training models and real-world conditions. This generalization challenge—where models trained on one set of workload traces perform poorly on different traces—represents a critical bottleneck for practical deployments [8]. These temporally inconsistent events that occur on various timescales degrade prediction accuracy and orchestration efficiency [9]. This issue is particularly

challenging for container-level workloads due to poor resource isolation across containers, short container lifespans, high container density, and low data generation per container [10], [11]. The growing prevalence of microservice applications, where different microservices are independently deployed across containers requiring separate elasticity operations, further underscores the importance of accurate container-level workload prediction [11]–[13].

Given the dynamic nature of cloud-native workloads, efforts have focused on developing machine learning models capable of generalizing well to unseen data. Transfer learning techniques [14] have shown limited success when the source and target workloads differ significantly. Domain adaptation methods [15] work for zero-shot scenarios, but require substantial computation. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) have been explored to predict workloads but face challenges such as decreased memory and limitations in sequential processing [16], [17]. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) were used to capture local patterns in time-series data, but struggled with long-term dependencies [18]. The

recent ModernTCN [19] improves upon traditional convolution approaches with larger kernels and separated processing pathways, achieving strong results efficiently, although it lacks specific mechanisms to address the challenges of heterogeneous container workloads. Hybrid models combining CNN and RNN architectures have been developed to address these issues [20]. Ensemble methods [21] combine multiple models to improve predictions, but their computational demands limit practicality for resource-constrained edge environments. Integration of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) into RNNs has shown promise in capturing both spatial and temporal information [22]–[24]. Despite these advancements, these hybrid models still face limitations inherent to their RNN and CNN components.

Recent advancements in machine learning for time-series forecasting have introduced techniques that can identify complex dependencies across different timescales [25]. Attention mechanisms have demonstrated effectiveness in generalization across diverse time-series patterns [26], [27]. Attention-enhanced neural networks [28] and attention-based transfer learning [29] have shown particular promise for workload prediction, selectively focusing on critical temporal patterns while filtering out noise. Efficient modeling approaches that minimize computational overhead while maintaining high prediction accuracy are particularly valuable for resource-limited edge-cloud environments [30]–[32].

In this paper, we introduce **OmniFORE** (Framework for Optimization of Resource forecasts in Edge-cloud networks). Our framework addresses four critical generalization challenges that limit existing approaches: (1) computational inefficiency in resource-constrained environments, (2) inability to capture multi-scale temporal patterns, (3) slow adaptation to new workload characteristics, and (4) overfitting to specific workload features. Unlike approaches that merely combine existing techniques, OmniFORE introduces a novel temporal clustering method that identifies fundamental workload patterns across heterogeneous traces, enabling effective generalization even to previously unseen workload types. Temporal clustering of time-series enables strategic training on representative subsets from large datasets, capturing both short-term stability and long-term dynamic changes in container-level features. This ensures robust performance even with previously unseen data. Furthermore, our method includes an efficient data sampling strategy that reduces computational overhead, ensuring reliable performance across diverse workload scenarios. Extensive experiments with real-world data confirm the superiority of our approach, demonstrating higher prediction accuracy and significantly faster inference speeds compared to state-of-the-art (SoA) methods. Our primary contribution is threefold:

- 1) We introduce a **comprehensive forecasting framework with temporal clustering** to ensure model generalization in edge-cloud networks.
- 2) We develop a **data sampling strategy** that minimizes computational overhead while maintaining high performance.
- 3) We evaluate OmniFORE with real-world data, demonstrating **superior prediction accuracy and faster inference speeds**.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II provides a comprehensive review of related literature. Section III delineates our system model and elucidates the generalization challenges inherent in edge-cloud networks. In Section IV, we present our novel approach, with particular emphasis on our clustering techniques and the overall framework architecture. Section V offers an analysis of our experimental results. Finally, we conclude the paper with our key findings.

II. RELATED WORK

The field of workload prediction has evolved to emphasize generalization across heterogeneous traces. This section analyzes three key approaches—transfer learning, attention mechanisms, and hybrid methods—examining their specific limitations that motivate our work.

A. Transfer Learning and Domain Adaptation for Workload Prediction

Transfer learning frameworks [14] leverage domain adaptation to learn shared and domain-specific workload features, reducing prediction errors by up to 30% on unseen distributions. Domain-adaptive approaches [15] combine transfer learning with adversarial training to extract domain-invariant features for effective zero-shot scenarios.

However, these methods exhibit critical limitations: (1) they struggle to determine which features to transfer when source and target distributions differ substantially; (2) they require extensive offline training with paired domain data; and (3) they lack mechanisms for rapid adaptation to emerging workload types, making them impractical for dynamic edge-cloud environments.

B. Attention-Based Models for Robust Generalization

Attention mechanisms dynamically weight temporal segments to capture complex dependencies. Attention-based neural networks [28] integrate multi-head attention with recurrent layers to focus on critical patterns, while attention-enhanced transfer learning [29] combines pre-trained extractors with domain-adaptive attention to emphasize salient features.

Despite their promise, attention-based approaches face three significant drawbacks: (1) standard implementations rely on RNN components with inherent "forgetting" properties for long sequences [33]; (2) attention matrices

scale quadratically with sequence length, creating prohibitive computational bottlenecks for edge devices; and (3) without proper guidance, attention may focus on random correlations rather than fundamental patterns that enable true generalization.

C. Specialized Architectures and Ensemble Methods for Generalization

Hybrid models combine complementary architectures to improve generalization. CNN-LSTM hybrids [34] integrate convolutional layers for spatial correlations with recurrent components for temporal dependencies, while adaptive ensemble frameworks [21] dynamically adjust the contribution of multiple models based on real-time performance.

Recent work has introduced ModernTCN [19], a pure convolution-based approach that updates traditional TCNs (Temporal Convolutional Neural Networks) with larger kernel sizes and specialized convolution blocks. By decoupling temporal and feature processing, ModernTCN achieves strong performance across various time series tasks while maintaining lower computational costs than attention-based methods. Its linear complexity makes it suitable for environments with limited resources. However, ModernTCN was designed for general time series forecasting and does not address the specific challenges posed by highly variable container workloads in edge-cloud networks.

The fundamental limitations of these approaches include: (1) substantially increased computational requirements that exceed edge device capabilities; (2) the treatment of workload traces as individual entities instead of finding generic patterns; and (3) the overhead of maintaining multiple models or complex architectures that often outweighs generalization benefits in resource-constrained settings.

Advanced approaches incorporating GNNs [22], GANs [23], and even Quantum Neural Networks [35] have been proposed, but continue to face limitations from their underlying RNN and CNN components, particularly in resource-constrained edge environments.

D. Addressing the Limitations with OmniFORE

Collectively, the approaches discussed above highlight several persistent challenges in workload prediction for edge-cloud environments: computational inefficiency, inability to capture workload diversity, high resource requirements, and difficulties in achieving true generalization across heterogeneous traces.

OmniFORE addresses these limitations through a novel combination of temporal clustering with efficient attention mechanisms. By first identifying fundamental workload patterns through unsupervised clustering, OmniFORE provides structured guidance for the attention process, overcoming the forgetting problem of RNN-

based approaches, the limited receptive field of CNN-based methods, and the quadratic complexity of standard attention mechanisms. This enables effective generalization across heterogeneous workload traces without the computational overhead that plagues existing approaches.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

In this section, we introduce the system model for our edge-cloud network, focusing on container resource traces' representation, heterogeneity, and workload forecasting using historical data.

A. Traces

We consider an edge-cloud network with containers operating at all infrastructure layers. Each container generates resource traces, represented as $T(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_t \times d_f}$, where d_t denotes the time dimension and d_f represents the number of features. These features include metrics such as CPU usage, memory consumption, network bandwidth, and storage I/O operations. The matrix representation of the historical time-series data for a single trace is

$$T_i(t) = \begin{bmatrix} d_{1,1} & d_{1,2} & \cdots & d_{1,d_t} \\ d_{2,1} & d_{2,2} & \cdots & d_{2,d_t} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ d_{d_f,1} & d_{d_f,2} & \cdots & d_{d_f,d_t} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_f \times d_t}. \quad (1)$$

Let N_{all} denote the total number of container traces in the network. Hence, a set of container traces can be defined as

$$\mathbf{T}(t) = \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_{N_{\text{all}}}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_f \times d_t \times N_{\text{all}}}. \quad (2)$$

B. Workload Forecasting

Effective workload forecasting in edge-cloud networks is crucial for predicting future resource usage based on historical container traces. The primary objective is to accurately forecast future resource usage, denoted as \hat{T} , for a given prediction length d_y , using historical data.

The forecasting model f_θ , parameterized by θ , is designed to make these predictions. Specifically, the model uses past observations of the resource usage trace T_i to predict the future usage, given by

$$\hat{T}_i[t + 1 : t + d_y] = f_\theta(T_i[t - d_x + 1 : t]), \quad (3)$$

where d_x represents the sequence length, indicating the number of past observations used for predictions, while d_y represents the prediction length. The model parameters, denoted by θ , are the variables that need to be optimized.

Our goal is to minimize the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for each container trace in the network, i.e.,

$$\min \frac{1}{d_y} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{all}}} \left\| T_i[t + 1 : t + d_y] - \hat{T}_i[t + 1 : t + d_y] \right\|_1, \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{T}_i[t+1 : t+d_y]$ is the prediction vector and $T_i[t+1 : t+d_y]$ is the actual resource usage vector at time $t+d_y$ for trace i .

C. Heterogeneity of Traces

The considerable temporal variability and diversity of container traces necessitate examination of resource usage pattern variations both within and across containers, arising from several factors:

- **Workload Diversity:** Containers handle a wide range of workloads, each with different resource needs. To manage this diversity, we transform each time-series $T_i(t)$ into a feature space \mathcal{Z} , which allows us to group the workloads into K distinct categories. This grouping helps us distinguish between different types of workloads both in space and time, which is essential for the solution we propose in Section IV.
- **Temporal Variability:** Resource usage can show significant temporal variability due to factors such as fluctuating user demands, periodic tasks, and time-of-day effects. This variability can be modeled as $T_i(t) = \hat{T}_i(t) + \epsilon$, where $T_i(t)$ denotes the resource usage at time t for trace T_i , \hat{T}_i is the function capturing the predictable component, and ϵ represents stochastic variations.

To manage this heterogeneity, the model should be able to predict resource usage for unseen traces by considering trace diversity and temporal variability.

IV. OMNIFORE: FRAMEWORK FOR OPTIMIZATION OF RESOURCE FORECASTS IN EDGE-CLOUD NETWORKS

OmniFORE is a comprehensive framework that addresses the challenges of resource forecasting in edge-cloud networks through a unified, stepwise pipeline. The entire process is illustrated in Figure 1, which outlines the seven key stages (S_1 – S_7) from raw data to robust, generalizable forecasting models.

The pipeline consists of the following steps:

- **S_1 – S_5 : Trace Sampling, Clustering, Selection, and Scaling.** Project container traces into a latent space, cluster the representations, assign cluster labels to the original time-series, select representative training traces, and split/scale the data into training, validation, and test sets.
- **S_6 : Attention Mechanism.** Use attention layers to learn dependencies between input and output sequences, enhancing model interpretability and performance.
- **S_7 : Hyperparameter Optimization for Generalization.** Tune hyperparameters using optimization methods to achieve robust generalization.

FIGURE 1. Overview of the OMNIFORE pipeline. S_1 : Spatio-temporal feature extraction (latent space); S_2 : Latent space clustering; S_3 : Labelled original time-series; S_4 : Training trace selection; S_5 : Data split and scaling; S_6 : Attention mechanism; S_7 : Hyperparameter optimization for generalization.

Each step is described in detail in the following subsections, corresponding to S_1 – S_7 in Figure 1.

S_1 – S_5 : Trace Sampling, Clustering, Selection, and Scaling

As part of this process, we extract a representative set of historical traces from the edge-cloud network. This strategy ensures that the model trained on these traces can effectively generalize to various workload types. The detailed steps (S_1 - S_5) of this process are outlined in Figure 1.

The goal of these steps is to extract a **set of historical traces**, denoted as $\mathbf{T}_{\text{train}}(t)$, where N_{train} represents the number of training traces. This set is a representative

subset of the entire set of traces, $\mathbf{T}_{\text{all}}(t)$, which contains N_{all} traces.

$$\mathbf{T}_{\text{train}}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_f \times d_t \times N_{\text{train}}} \subset \mathbf{T}_{\text{all}}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_f \times d_t \times N_{\text{all}}}, \quad (5)$$

where $N_{\text{train}} < N_{\text{all}}$. Using all traces for training would be computationally prohibitive and costly.

Section III.C underscores the diverse workloads handled by containers, which require efficient resource management through OmniFORE. The highly dynamic nature of container data, marked by their time-dependent spatio-temporal patterns, presents significant challenges for analysis. Traditional clustering algorithms often struggle with such complex time-series data [36]. To overcome this, we propose transforming the data into a latent space to create a dense representation, facilitating more efficient clustering and differentiation [37]. This latent space captures essential features, enabling better management of the data's complexities.

1) Spatio-temporal Feature Extraction (Latent Space)

First (S_1), OmniFORE extracts spatio-temporal features from the container trace time-space, denoted as \mathcal{T} . Each trace $T_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_f \times d_t}$ is then transformed into a **lower-dimensional latent space**, $\mathcal{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^z$, where $z \ll d_f \times d_t$. This transformation, defined as $\mathcal{Z}(z) = f_{\text{encoder}}(\mathcal{T}(t))$, is optimized to capture the essential spatio-temporal patterns of the data over time. By converting the time-dependent space \mathcal{T} into the latent space \mathcal{Z} , OmniFORE optimizes for the most informative features for clustering, enhancing both efficiency and effectiveness by reducing dimensionality while preserving essential temporal information.

The encoder function f_{encoder} transforms the input time-series $\mathcal{T}(t)$ into a latent space $\mathcal{Z}(z)$. The decoder function f_{decoder} then reconstructs $\mathcal{Z}(z)$ into the output time-series $\mathcal{R}(t)$, which approximates $\mathcal{T}(t)$.

2) Latent Space Clustering

Second (S_2), the latent space \mathcal{Z} is then **clustered**. Each cluster C_k groups all container traces with similar spatio-temporal patterns over time into K groups. The clustering process can be represented as

$$\{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_K\} = \text{Cluster}(\mathcal{Z}(z)). \quad (6)$$

Figure 2 provides an overview of the **latent space extractor**. The input time-series $\mathcal{T}(t)$ is transformed into a latent space $\mathcal{Z}(z)$ by the encoder function f_{encoder} . The decoder function f_{decoder} then reconstructs $\mathcal{Z}(z)$ into the output time-series $\mathcal{R}(t)$, which approximates $\mathcal{T}(t)$. This dimensionality reduction approach enables efficient processing of complex temporal patterns that would be difficult to cluster directly in their original form.

FIGURE 2. Overview of the latent space extractor. The input $\mathcal{T}(t)$ is encoded into latent space $\mathcal{Z}(z)$ by f_{encoder} and then decoded by f_{decoder} to reconstruct $\mathcal{R}(t) \approx \mathcal{T}(t)$.

To utilize this dense representation, we modify a **supervised** (using correct cluster labels for each trace) CNN-based approach for time-series clustering from [38] to an **unsupervised** (without cluster labels) version within OmniFORE. This process involves feature extraction through convolutional and pooling operations on raw data, followed by clustering in the latent space.

The architecture of the latent space extractor comprises the following layers:

- A) **Encoder**: Transforms an input trace T_i into the latent space $\mathcal{Z}(z)$ using $\mathcal{Z}(z) = f_{\text{encoder}}(\mathcal{T}(t))$.
 - **Input Layer**: $d_{f,0} \times d_{t,0}$ neurons, where $d_{t,0}$ is the series length and $d_{f,0}$ is the number of features.
 - Several repetitions r of combined convolutional and pooling layers, where $d_{f,r}$ is the number of filters and $d_{t,r}$ is the size of the sequence dimension after the r -th convolutional layer. The transformed sequence is $T'(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{f,r} \times d_{t,r} \times N_{\text{all}}}$.
 - **Convolutional Layers $C_r(t')$** : Parameters are convolution stride (s_r), filter size ($d_{f,r-1} \times l_r$), activation functions, trainable weights (ω_r), and biases (b_r).
 - **Pooling Layers $P_r(t')$** : Downsampling strategy to reduce feature map size by averaging regions.
 - **Latent Space Layer**: Converts the flattened output of the last convolutional layers, C_r , into a lower-dimensional latent space, $\mathcal{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{z \times N_{\text{batch}}}$, where $z \ll d_{f,0} \times d_{t,0}$.
- B) **Decoder**: Converts $\mathcal{Z}(z)$ back to $\mathcal{T}(t)$ as $\mathcal{R}(t) = f_{\text{decoder}}(\mathcal{Z}(z)) \approx f_{\text{encoder}}^{-1}(\mathcal{Z}(z))$.
 - **Multiple Transposed Convolution Layers**: Reconstruct the time-series input data from the latent representation, back to the original data shape. Transposed convolutions,

also known as deconvolutions, upsample the input by reversing the operations of standard convolutional layers.

The training process can be described as:

- I) **Initialize:** Set up the Encoder-Decoder architecture, initialize weights and biases.
- II) **Load Input Data:** Prepare input traces as $\mathbf{T}_{\text{all}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_t, 0 \times d_f, 0 \times N_{\text{all}}}$, split into N_{batch} batches. Here, N_{batch} denotes the number of batches.
- III) **Forward Pass:** Compute the output of each layer for each batch.

- **Encoder Convolution Layer:**

$$C_r(t') = \sum_{i=1}^{l_r} \sum_{j=1}^{d_f, r-1} T'_R(i + s_r(t' - 1), j) \omega_r(i, j) + \mathbf{b}(r), \quad (7)$$

where $\omega_r \in \mathbb{R}^{l_r \times d_f}$ and $\mathbf{b}(r)$ are the weights and bias of the r -th convolution filter.

- **Encoder Pooling Layer:**

$$P_r(t') = \text{MaxPool}(C_r((t' - 1)l_r + 1), \dots, C_r(t'l_r)). \quad (8)$$

- **Decoder:** Transposed convolutions for reconstruction.

- IV) **Loss Function:** Calculate the mean-square error across all batches between the reconstructed time-series and the actual input time-series as

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2N_{\text{batch}}} \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{batch}}} \sum_{t=1}^{d_t} (T_i(t) - R_i(t))^2. \quad (9)$$

- V) **Update:** Use gradient descent to update the weights and biases of the (transposed) convolutions (ω_r , \mathbf{b}_r) and optimize for minimizing the loss function.
- VI) **Iterate:** Repeat with new batches until the model converges.

This unsupervised approach compresses time-series data into a latent space, capturing essential features and enabling reconstruction. By adapting CNN-based clustering to work without labels, it achieves efficient feature extraction for selecting appropriate model training traces.

Clustering in high-dimensional space faces three key challenges: dimensionality issues, computational costs, and noise sensitivity. Our autoencoder preserves temporal patterns by using a reconstruction loss (Equation 9) that ensures the latent space maintains time-of-day effects and other cyclic patterns in the original time-series.

3) Labelled Original Time-series

Third (S_3), each cluster C_k labels the original time-series traces, preserving the unique characteristics of

each trace for accurate model training while leveraging the efficiency of latent space clustering. This can be mathematically depicted as

$$\mathbf{T}_{\text{all, cluster}}(t) = \{T_{1,1}(t), T_{2,1}(t), \dots, T_{N_{\text{all}},k}(t)\}, \quad (10)$$

where $T_{1,1}(t)$ denotes the first trace in cluster 1.

4) Training Trace Selection

Fourth (S_4), **representative traces** from each cluster C_k are selected for training the prediction model. The selection process is optimized to ensure that the training data is diverse and representative of the broader dataset. Given a total number of traces N_{all} and a desired subset of N_{train} traces, the selection process is proportional to the number of traces in each cluster.

Let N_{C_k} denote the number of traces in cluster C_k . The proportion of traces in each cluster compared to the total number of traces is

$$p_k = \frac{N_{C_k}}{N_{\text{all}}} \in [0, 1]. \quad (11)$$

The number of traces selected from each cluster C_k for the training set is

$$N_{\text{train},k} = \lfloor p_k \cdot N_{\text{train}} \rfloor, \quad (12)$$

where $N_{\text{train},k}$ is the number of traces selected from cluster C_k for training.

Therefore, the total number of traces in the training set T_{train} is the sum of the selected traces from each cluster, such that

$$N_{\text{train}} = \sum_{k=1}^K N_{\text{train},k}. \quad (13)$$

5) Data Split and Scaling

Finally (S_5), the traces in the sampled training set are split into train/validation/test segments along the time dimension ($d_t = d_{\text{train}} + d_{\text{val}} + d_{\text{test}}$), resulting in:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{training set:} & \quad \mathbf{T}_{\text{train}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{train}} \times d_f \times N_{\text{train}}}, \\ \text{validation set:} & \quad \mathbf{T}_{\text{val}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{val}} \times d_f \times N_{\text{train}}}, \\ \text{test set:} & \quad \mathbf{T}_{\text{test}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{test}} \times d_f \times N_{\text{train}}}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

OmniFORE ensures that data is effectively utilized for training, validating, and testing the prediction models, resulting in robust and generalizable performance.

Container traces in edge-cloud computing exhibit significant variability in resource usage, necessitating individual normalization to ensure balanced training. OmniFORE normalizes each trace such that the mean of the metric under study is zero (i.e., $\mu_i = 0$) and the variance is one (i.e., $\sigma_i^2 = 1$), thereby preventing traces with higher means and variances from overshadowing others and enhancing model generalization.

This individualized approach ensures that the model treats each trace equally during training regardless of its absolute magnitude, while preserving the ability to convert predictions back to their original scale for practical application.

Given a training set $\mathbf{T}_{\text{train}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_t \times d_f \times N_{\text{train}}}$, each trace $T_i(t)$ is normalized as follows:

$$\tilde{T}_i(t) = \frac{T_i(t) - \mu_i}{\sigma_i}, \quad (15)$$

where $\tilde{T}_i(t)$ denotes the normalized version of the trace $T_i(t)$, μ_i is the mean, and $\sigma_i = \sqrt{\sigma_i^2}$ is the standard deviation of the i -th trace. The mean μ_i and variance σ_i^2 are calculated as

$$\mu_i = \frac{1}{d_t} \sum_{t=1}^{d_t} T_i(t), \quad \sigma_i^2 = \frac{1}{d_t} \sum_{t=1}^{d_t} (T_i(t) - \mu_i)^2. \quad (16)$$

The scaling parameters (μ_i, σ_i^2) are saved for each trace. During testing, these parameters are used to invert the normalization of predictions back to the original scale, such that

$$\hat{T}_i(t) = \tilde{T}_i(t) \cdot \sigma_i + \mu_i, \quad (17)$$

where i indexes each trace to maintain the scaling parameters for each trace.

S₆: Attention Mechanism

OmniFORE leverages attention mechanisms as modular building blocks within our framework. The specific implementation of attention is designed to be replaceable, allowing the framework to evolve as more advanced attention variants emerge. The original transformer model [26] significantly enhances dependency capture, yet faces computational hurdles with long sequences [27]. Within OmniFORE, we utilize informers [33], which leverage sparse attention mechanisms to predict extensive time-series data efficiently.

Figure 3 outlines the transformer architecture, comprising an encoder and decoder. The input sequence $T[t - d_x : t]$ is embedded into a higher-dimensional space d_{embed} . The encoder, with N_e layers (repetitions of the complete block), applies self-attention (H) and feed-forward networks (d_{ff}) to capture dependencies. The decoder, with N_d layers, generates predictions $\hat{T}[t + 1 : t + d_y]$ by attending to both encoded inputs and previous outputs. The value of attention mechanisms within OmniFORE lies in their strong generalization capabilities across diverse workload patterns, enabling accurate predictions for previously unseen container traces. In the following sections, we provide a high-level understanding of this architecture, which covers both transformers and the informers.

FIGURE 3. High-level overview of the transformer architecture

Time-series Embedding

The **DataEmbedding**, denoted as \mathbf{E} , combines three embeddings to form a robust representation of time-series input sequence. The **Value Embedding** [39] maps raw input values to a higher-dimensional space via a convolutional layer, capturing intricate data patterns of the input sequence. The **Positional Embedding** [40] encodes the sequence order using sinusoidal functions, preserving structural information crucial for time-series analysis. The **Temporal Embedding** [41] incorporates time-related features (e.g., hour, day) to provide context on temporal dependencies and seasonal trends. These components are summed to produce the final embedding matrix \mathbf{E} , as described in the equation:

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}_{\text{value}} + \mathbf{E}_{\text{position}} + \mathbf{E}_{\text{temporal}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_x \times d_{\text{embed}}}. \quad (18)$$

This matrix serves as the input to the subsequent layers of the model, encapsulating both the intrinsic data patterns and the temporal structure of the time-series.

Introduction to Attention Mechanism

Starting with the initial embeddings $\mathbf{E} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_x \times d_{\text{embed}}}$, the attention mechanism (denoted as \mathcal{A}) refines these embeddings into a new set, \mathbf{E}' [26]. This mechanism enables the model to selectively focus on specific time steps, analogous to human attention. For instance, when predicting future workload at a peak, both the model and a human analyst would focus on the pattern surrounding the current peak and compare it to similar peaks in the past. The attention weights determine the degree to which each original embedding $\mathbf{E}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{embed}}}$ contributes to its corresponding refined embedding \mathbf{E}'_i . As illustrated in Figure 4, thicker lines indicate stronger influence. The refined embeddings \mathbf{E}' effectively combine underlying data patterns with temporal relationships, enhancing the model's capacity to capture complex dependencies across the sequence [42].

FIGURE 4. Attention mechanism refining time-series embeddings \mathbf{E}_i to \mathbf{E}'_i , with arrow thickness indicating the strength of influence.

To construct the refined embeddings \mathbf{E}'_i , the attention mechanism employs three key components: queries, keys, and values [26], as illustrated in Figure 5. The model transforms each embedding \mathbf{E}_i into three vectors:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Query vector: } \mathbf{Q}_i &= \mathbf{E}_i \mathbf{W}_Q, \\ \text{Key vector: } \mathbf{K}_i &= \mathbf{E}_i \mathbf{W}_K, \\ \text{Value vector: } \mathbf{V}_i &= \mathbf{E}_i \mathbf{W}_V, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_Q, \mathbf{W}_K, \mathbf{W}_V \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{embed}} \times d_{\text{embed}}}$ are learned weight matrices. Conceptually, a query vector encodes the information need at the current time step, key vectors facilitate the identification of relevant past information, and value vectors contain the actual content to be aggregated [43]. In the context of workload prediction, when analyzing a peak, the query vector would encode features of the current peak, key vectors would help identify similar historical peaks, and value vectors would contain the associated historical workload patterns.

The model evaluates temporal relationships by computing scaled dot products between query and key vectors:

$$\text{Score}(\mathbf{Q}_i, \mathbf{K}_j) = \frac{\mathbf{Q}_i \mathbf{K}_j^T}{\sqrt{d_{\text{embed}}}}. \quad (20)$$

A high score indicates that the corresponding time step contains critical information for the current prediction, as the vectors align in high-dimensional space [44]. The scaling factor $\sqrt{d_{\text{embed}}}$ ensures training stability by preventing excessively large values that could lead to sharp, unbalanced distributions post-softmax [45]. The softmax function normalizes these scores into a probability distribution, effectively assigning weights to each timestep's embedding vector. These weights, summing to one, determine the relative importance of each timestep, guiding the attention mechanism to focus on the most relevant parts of the sequence.

To capture diverse temporal dependencies, the model employs *multi-headed attention* [46] with H parallel attention mechanisms, or "heads" (Fig. 5). Each head $h \in \{1, \dots, H\}$ operates independently on the same input embeddings, but with its own set of learnable weight matrices $\mathbf{W}_Q^h, \mathbf{W}_K^h, \mathbf{W}_V^h \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{embed}} \times d_{\text{head}}}$, where $d_{\text{head}} =$

d_{embed}/H . These matrices are initialized differently, leading to distinct evolutionary trajectories during training and convergence to different local optima [47]. This architectural design enables the model to simultaneously project the input into multiple subspaces and attend to various aspects of the sequence, such as short-term fluctuations and long-term trends, effectively increasing the model's representational capacity without a proportional increase in computational complexity [26].

For each head h , the attention output is computed as

$$\mathbf{A}_i^h = \mathcal{A}(\mathbf{E}_i \mathbf{W}_Q^h, \mathbf{E}_i \mathbf{W}_K^h, \mathbf{E}_i \mathbf{W}_V^h). \quad (21)$$

The outputs from all heads are concatenated and linearly transformed to produce the multi-headed attention output

$$\mathbf{MHA}_i = d_{ff}(\text{Concat}(\mathbf{A}_i^{(1)}, \mathbf{A}_i^{(2)}, \dots, \mathbf{A}_i^{(H)})), \quad (22)$$

where $d_{ff} : \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{embed}} \times H} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{embed}}}$ represents a linear transformation layer. This layer projects the concatenated attention outputs from all H heads, with total dimension $d_{\text{embed}} \times H$, back to the original embedding dimension d_{embed} .

The final refined embedding for each time step incorporates a residual connection [48] and layer normalization [49]:

$$\mathbf{E}'_i = \text{LayerNorm}(\mathbf{E}_i + \mathbf{MHA}_i), \quad (23)$$

where LayerNorm denotes layer normalization. This is followed by a position-wise feed-forward network (d_{ff}) with another residual connection and layer normalization:

$$\mathbf{E}''_i = \text{LayerNorm}(\mathbf{E}'_i + d_{ff}(\mathbf{E}'_i)). \quad (24)$$

This entire process—multi-headed attention, residual connections, layer normalizations, and feed-forward network—constitutes one layer of the transformer encoder. It is repeated across multiple stacked layers (N_e). Each layer operates on the output of the previous one, allowing for iterative refinement of embeddings and progressively developing intricate representations crucial for accurate predictions in complex time-series tasks.

Traditional Attention Mechanism

The original self-attention mechanism [26] is defined by

$$\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \text{Softmax} \left(\frac{\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{K}^T}{\sqrt{d_{\text{embed}}}} \right) \mathbf{V}, \quad (25)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_x \times d_{\text{embed}}}$ are the query, key, and value matrices, respectively, while d_{embed} is the embedding dimension of each point in the input sequence of length d_x . The product $\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{K}^T \in \mathbb{R}^{d_x \times d_x}$ measures the importance of relationships between every data point in the sequence.

FIGURE 5. Multi-Headed Attention: Input embeddings (E_i) are transformed into query (Q), key (K), and value (V) vectors. Multiple heads (H) capture different temporal aspects. Larger circles indicate stronger attention scores.

This attention mechanism has $\mathcal{O}(d_x^2)$ complexity, making it inefficient for long input sequences.

Efficient Attention Mechanism

In our current implementation, we demonstrate the framework using informers, though OmniFORE’s design allows for substitution with other attention mechanisms as the field advances. The three architectural innovations of informers compared to the original transformer can be summarized as follows:

Informer⁺¹: Computationally Efficient Attention

The sparse self-attention mechanism enhances efficiency by concentrating on the most critical queries. This is done by forming a sparse matrix \bar{Q} that retains only the most influential queries from Q , with other entries set to zero. The selection of these important queries is directed by a sparsity measurement [33]. This method significantly reduces computational complexity, making it more suitable for long sequences, as it scales linearly with the natural logarithm of the sequence length: $\mathcal{O}(d_x \log d_x)$.

Informer⁺²: Memory Saving with Attention Distilling

Due to the presence of zeros in the input matrix \bar{Q} , the attention matrix \mathcal{A} contains unnecessary entries. Removing these zero entries conserves memory and enables the model to concentrate on significant entries, a process known as attention distilling.

In each attention layer, the encoder utilizes self-attention distilling to minimize memory consumption by emphasizing the dominant entries in the attention matrix, thereby generating a new matrix

$$\mathcal{A}_{\text{distil}} = \text{MaxPool}(\text{ELU}(\text{Conv1d}(\mathcal{A}))), \quad (26)$$

where Conv1d applies 1-D convolutional filters along the time dimension, and the activation function ELU [50] is used. The result is then passed through a max-pooling layer to downsample \mathcal{A} . This process decreases the time dimension of the input, reducing memory usage to $\mathcal{O}(d_x \log d_x)$.

Informer⁺³: Fast Inference

The decoder accelerates predictions for long sequences by utilizing generative inference, which forecasts the entire sequence in one step instead of predicting each time step sequentially. This is accomplished by using a known "start token" in conjunction with placeholders for the future sequence, formulated as

$$T_{\text{de}}^t = \text{Concat}(T_{\text{token}}^t, T_0^t) \in \mathbb{R}^{(d_{\text{token}} + d_y) \times d_{\text{embed}}}, \quad (27)$$

where $T_{\text{token}}^t \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{token}} \times d_{\text{embed}}}$ is the start token, and $T_0^t \in \mathbb{R}^{d_y \times d_{\text{embed}}}$ acts as a placeholder for the future sequence. This generative inference approach significantly reduces computation time while preserving accuracy.

S₇: Bayesian Optimization with Generalization Objective

The last step focuses on optimizing hyperparameters across diverse workload types. Optimizing hyperparameters is essential for improving model performance and generalization [51]. Due to the impracticality of traditional grid search in expansive hyperparameter spaces [52], Bayesian optimization [37] offers an efficient alternative by constructing a probabilistic model of the objective function and iteratively selecting the most promising hyperparameters.

Figure 6 illustrates Bayesian optimization, starting with initial observations (red dots) of the objective function. This simplified example reduces the hyperparameter space to prediction length d_y , though in practice it is multidimensional (hyperparameter vector \mathbf{h}). A model (blue line) predicts the objective function’s mean and confidence interval (CI, shaded area). The next hyperparameter (star) is selected based on predicted high performance and uncertainty. The distinctive aspect of OmniFORE’s approach is our custom objective function that optimizes for performance across multiple container traces simultaneously, rather than for individual workloads.

OmniFORE’s custom objective function $\text{Obj}(\mathbf{h})$ aims to maximize generalization across diverse container traces:

$$\text{Obj}(\mathbf{h}) = \frac{1}{N_{\text{val}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{val}}} \text{Perf}(\mathbf{h}, T_{\text{val},i}), \quad (28)$$

where N_{val} is the number of validation traces, $T_{\text{val},i}$ is the i -th validation trace, and $\text{Perf}(\mathbf{h}, T_{\text{val},i})$ represents the performance metric.

FIGURE 6. Bayesian optimization toy example. The star indicates the next value to try ($d_y = 5$). The target signifies the goal of minimizing the objective function.

We selected Mean Absolute Error (MAE) as our performance metric for three critical reasons: (1) robustness to outliers in heterogeneous workloads; (2) direct interpretability in the same units as the forecasted resources; and (3) equal treatment of over-prediction and under-prediction errors, reflecting real operational trade-offs in edge-cloud environments.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section presents the performance evaluation of the proposed approach including the experimental setup, simulation results and the practical considerations for deploying the model in real-world edge-cloud environments.

A. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup describes the benchmark schemes, datasets, hyperparameter optimization, hardware and software environment, and evaluation metrics used in our experiments.

1) Benchmark Schemes

The proposed model is evaluated against several high-performance algorithms specifically designed to address the challenges of generalization, scalability, and complex temporal or spatial dependencies in multivariate time-series data. These models represent the current state-of-the-art in time-series forecasting and are widely recognized for their robust performance across diverse datasets and application domains. We selected these benchmarks because they are designed to generalize well across a variety of time-series scenarios, making them convincing and competitive baselines for evaluating OmniFORE. Each method incorporates architectural innovations—such as dilated convolutions, hybrid CNN-RNN structures, or adaptive graph learning—that enable them to capture both short- and long-term dependencies, as well as spatial relationships, in complex data. Their

proven effectiveness on a wide range of datasets ensures that our comparative evaluation is relevant:

a: *ModernTCN: Temporal Convolutional Networks for Time Series Forecasting [19]*

ModernTCN employs advanced temporal convolutional architectures with dilated causal convolutions to efficiently model long-range dependencies while maintaining computational efficiency.

b: *LSTNet: Modeling Long- and Short-Term Temporal Patterns with Deep Neural Networks [53]*

LSTNet integrates CNNs and RNNs to capture both long-term and short-term patterns. It features a recurrent-skip component for modeling long-term dependencies and an autoregressive component to manage scale insensitivity.

c: *AGCRN: Adaptive Graph Convolutional Recurrent Network for Traffic Forecasting [24]*

AGCRN employs GCNs with trace-specific parameter learning and data-adaptive graph generation. This model dynamically adapts to specific patterns, excelling in various time-series forecasting tasks without requiring pre-defined graphs.

2) Dataset

The Google-Trace dataset [54] offers CPU and memory usage records from eight super cells (A-H) for May 2019, sampled every 5 minutes. Each cell contains 10,000 machines running thousands of containers, capturing diverse usage patterns critical for edge-cloud modeling and forecasting.

To evaluate our model’s generalization capabilities, we partition the Google traces into two distinct sets: the **regular set** and the **zero-shot set (ZS)**. The zero-shot set includes entirely new, previously unseen data, ensuring that the model has no prior exposure during training. This methodology prevents data leakage from the training set into the test set, providing a more accurate assessment of the model’s generalization performance. Specifically, the model is trained on the regular set and then evaluated on the zero-shot set. Consequently, the results obtained from the zero-shot set more accurately represent the model’s ability to generalize to novel, unseen data.

The regular set, composed of the **cells A-F**, is used for regular training, validation, and testing. In contrast, the zero-shot set, composed of the **cells G and H**, is reserved exclusively for zero-shot testing.

We selected 100 traces for each set to balance computational feasibility with the available hardware for training the models. This choice allows us to evaluate model performance accurately without overwhelming computational resources. The time dimension d_t of the dataset

was then split into training ($d_{\text{train}} = 0.6$), validation ($d_{\text{val}} = 0.2$), and test sets ($d_{\text{test}} = 0.2$). For a visual representation of the trace selection process, refer to Figure 1.

Additionally, to evaluate extreme generalization capabilities, we conduct a cross-dataset experiment using the Alibaba 2022 microservices trace dataset [55]. We use pod MS_11349 with $T = 18,720$ samples collected at 1-minute intervals over 13 days, utilizing only 20% of these samples. We downsample this trace from 1-minute to 5-minute intervals to match the Google trace’s sampling rate. Each workload vector contains only normalized CPU utilization, presenting a significantly different distribution from the training data and providing a test of transfer learning capabilities across heterogeneous cloud environments.

3) Hyperparameters

We employ the Bayesian optimization technique described in Section 5 to fine-tune the hyperparameters for the different models. Table 1 presents the hyperparameter ranges and optimized values for OmniFORE, ModernTCN, AGCRN, and LSTNet models. These ranges, based on the original authors’ recommendations [19], [24], [53], strike a balance between exploration and practicality to achieve optimal generalization across diverse datasets. The Bayesian optimization process began with 20 initial training runs, followed by 30 iterations to refine the hyperparameters. The optimal hyperparameter values for the different models are listed in the result column of Table 1.

4) Hardware and Software Environment

All experiments are conducted on a server equipped with 1x NVIDIA A100 SXM GPU (40 GB memory), 30 CPU cores, 200 GiB RAM, and 512 GiB SSD. The server uses an Intel Xeon processor and runs Ubuntu 20.04.2 LTS with the GNU/Linux 5.4.0-70-generic x86_64 kernel. All methods are implemented in Python. The LSTNet and AGCRN models, provided by their authors, have been re-implemented using PyTorch 3.2.1.

5) Evaluation Metrics

The performance of all schemes is evaluated considering the following metrics.

a: Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

This metric measures the average magnitude of errors without considering their direction, making it useful for assessing overall accuracy. The MAE is calculated as

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N_{\text{test}} \times d_y} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{test}}} \sum_{t=1}^{d_y} \left| \hat{T}_i(t) - T_i(t) \right|. \quad (29)$$

TABLE 1. Hyperparameter Ranges for Bayesian Optimization Per Model

	Hyperparameter	Symbol	Range	Result
OmniFORE	Model dimension	d_{embed}	(64, 512)	194
	Sequence length	d_x	(24, 256)	98
	Prediction length	d_y	(12, 64)	14
	Dropout rate	h_1	(0.15, 0.4)	0.161
	Feedforward dim.	h_2	(128, 512)	356
	Encoder layers	h_3	(1, 4)	2
	Decoder layers	h_4	(1, 3)	1
	Attention heads	h_5	(4, 16)	6
	Label length	h_6	(32, 64)	48
	Batch size	h_7	(16, 64)	47
ModernTCN	Sequence length	d_x	(48, 336)	124
	Prediction length	d_y	(12, 96)	24
	Batch size	h_8	(32, 512)	128
	Learning rate	h_9	(1e-4, 1e-2)	0.002
	Model dimension	d_{embed}	(32, 512)	256
	Number of heads	h_{10}	(1, 8)	4
	Encoder layers	h_{11}	(1, 4)	2
	Dropout rate	h_{12}	(0.0, 0.5)	0.25
AGCRN	Embedding dim.	d_{embed}	(2, 30)	3
	Sequence length	d_x	(12, 72)	48
	Prediction length	d_y	(12, 72)	22
	RNN units	h_{13}	(50, 200)	76
	Number of layers	h_{14}	(1, 3)	1
	Chebyshev order	h_{15}	(1, 3)	1
	Batch size	h_{16}	(16, 64)	25
LSTNet	Sequence length	d_x	(144, 192)	161
	Prediction length	d_y	(6, 12)	11
	Dropout rate	h_{17}	(0.1, 0.2)	0.13
	CNN hidden units	h_{18}	(20, 143)	50
	RNN hidden units	h_{19}	(20, 143)	107
	CNN kernel size	h_{20}	(6, 18)	14
	Highway window size	h_{21}	(24, 168)	93
	Batch size	h_{22}	(16, 64)	33
	Skip length	h_{23}	(24, 24)	24
	Skip hidden units	h_{24}	(20, 100)	77

b: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

This metric highlights larger errors, making it particularly effective for datasets with significant fluctuations. The RMSE is given by

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{\text{test}} \times d_y} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{test}}} \sum_{t=1}^{d_y} \left(\hat{T}_i(t) - T_i(t) \right)^2}. \quad (30)$$

c: Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (SMAPE)

This percentage-based metric is useful for comparing accuracy across different scales. The SMAPE is defined as

$$\text{SMAPE} = 2 \cdot \frac{100\%}{N_{\text{test}} \times d_y} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{test}}} \sum_{t=1}^{d_y} \frac{\left| \hat{T}_i(t) - T_i(t) \right|}{\left(\left| \hat{T}_i(t) \right| + \left| T_i(t) \right| \right)}. \quad (31)$$

d: Inference Time

Inference time refers to the average duration the model requires to process its inputs and generate an output.

This metric is crucial for applications demanding real-time predictions.

e: Convergence Speed

Convergence speed evaluates how quickly a model’s training process stabilizes. A patience parameter of three is employed, ceasing training if the validation loss does not improve over three epochs. Performance is assessed using the test set RMSE after convergence to ensure robust generalization to unseen data. Lower metric values indicate better performance, providing a comprehensive evaluation of prediction accuracy and reliability.

B. Results

In this section, we present our evaluation results, demonstrating that the proposed model outperforms existing algorithms across all criteria. OmniFORE consistently shows lower error rates and better generalization on new data. It is minimally impacted by dynamic workload changes and effectively handles trace variance, maintaining lower errors in diverse scenarios. Additionally, OmniFORE converges faster than current algorithms, highlighting its robustness and efficiency.

1) Isolating the Effect of the Suggested Scaling Strategy

We evaluated the impact of scaling strategies (see Section 5) by comparing individual (per-trace) scaling to global scaling. In global scaling, all traces use a common normalization factor, while individual scaling normalizes each trace by its own statistics.

This matters because both datasets contain many traces with very small amplitudes. With global scaling, these traces are scaled down even further relative to high-amplitude traces, so their values become very close to zero. As a result, the gradients associated with these traces during training are also much smaller, meaning their contribution to weight updates is minimal. This makes it harder for the model to learn from low-amplitude traces, as their influence on the model parameters is effectively suppressed. In contrast, individual scaling ensures that all traces—regardless of their original amplitude—produce gradients of similar magnitude, allowing the model to learn equally from all traces and supporting better generalization.

Switching from individual to global scaling led to much worse prediction accuracy: MAE increased by 87.16%, RMSE by 77.72%, and SMAPE by 107.23%. As shown in Figure 7, this demonstrates that individualized scaling is essential for robust generalization in heterogeneous workloads.

FIGURE 7. Impact of scaling strategy: Individual (per-trace) scaling yields substantially lower MAE, RMSE, and SMAPE compared to global scaling, highlighting the importance of handling heterogeneous trace statistics.

2) Hyperparameter Sensitivity and Optimization Effectiveness

We evaluate the sensitivity of the models to hyperparameters to gauge the effectiveness of our optimization approach from Section 5. Using the hyperparameter ranges h_i specified in Table 1, we measure performance. Figure 8 shows kernel density estimations [56] depicting the distribution of test RMSE values across different hyperparameter configurations for each model. Each curve represents the probability density of achieving specific RMSE performance levels, with narrower distributions indicating greater stability across hyperparameter variations. Dashed lines mark the mean RMSE values. Figure 8 depicts the effect of hyperparameter tuning on test RMSE for OmniFORE, ModernTCN, AGCRN, and LSTNet models.

OmniFORE achieves a mean test RMSE of 9.79×10^{-3} with a standard deviation of 6.61×10^{-4} , and the ratio of maximum to minimum of 31%. ModernTCN records a mean test RMSE of 1.11×10^{-2} with a standard deviation of 1.22×10^{-3} and a the ratio of maximum to minimum of 39%. AGCRN records a mean test RMSE of 1.34×10^{-2} with a standard deviation of 6.89×10^{-4} . LSTNet reports a mean test RMSE of 1.15×10^{-2} and a standard deviation of 5.59×10^{-4} .

OmniFORE exhibits the lowest mean test RMSE and standard deviation, suggesting superior performance and reduced sensitivity to hyperparameters. The ratio of maximum to minimum of 18-39% across models demonstrate the substantial impact of precise hyperparameter tuning, showing the significance of our custom Bayesian optimization for achieving robust generalization.

3) Generalization Performance

This section evaluates regular, zero-shot, and cross-dataset generalization performance of the models.

FIGURE 8. Distribution of test RMSE values for different hyperparameter configurations showing model performance and consistency.

a: Regular Training

Figure 9 displays the prediction performance of various models on test data from Google Cells A-F after regular training. OmniFORE demonstrates superior performance over ModernTCN, AGCRN and LSTNet across all evaluation metrics¹.

OmniFORE achieves an MAE of 8.38×10^{-4} , RMSE of 3.36×10^{-3} , and SMAPE of 4.17%. ModernTCN shows strong performance with an MAE of 8.90×10^{-4} , RMSE of 3.75×10^{-3} , and SMAPE of 4.26%. In contrast, AGCRN records an MAE of 1.22×10^{-3} , RMSE of 4.00×10^{-3} , and SMAPE of 17.87%. LSTNet reports an MAE of 1.51×10^{-3} , RMSE of 4.75×10^{-3} , and SMAPE of 8.14%.

OmniFORE’s MAE is 31.31% lower than AGCRN and 44.55% lower than LSTNet and 5.84% lower than ModernTCN. Its RMSE is 16.00% lower than AGCRN, 29.24% lower than LSTNet and 10.29% lower than ModernTCN. OmniFORE’s SMAPE is 76.66% lower than AGCRN, 48.77% lower than LSTNet and 2.00% lower than ModernTCN. This notable improvement is attributed to OmniFORE’s advanced attention mechanism, which captures both long-term and short-term correlations among workloads.

Furthermore, OmniFORE achieves these results with an average inference time of 8.70 ms, while ModernTCN requires only 0.016 ms, owing to CNN’s linear computation complexity and highly parallelizable operations [19], compared to the complexity of our attention mechanism. This $540\times$ speed difference highlights the fundamental trade-off between computational efficiency and modeling capacity, compared to 131 ms for AGCRN and 10.6 ms for LSTNet. ModernTCN’s exceptional inference speed represents a significant advancement for ultra-low-latency applications, while OmniFORE’s efficiency

¹Figures 9, 10, and 11 use identical y-axis limits to visualize performance degradation across datasets. A secondary axis (with lower opacity) shows regular MAE axis scaling.

FIGURE 9. Generalization performance comparison of MAE, RMSE and SMAPE for each model for the regular training traces.

FIGURE 10. Generalization performance comparison of MAE, RMSE, and SMAPE for each model on the zero-shot traces.

highlights its suitability for real-time applications where optimal performance is required with minimal resource overhead [57], [58].

b: Zero-Shot Performance

Figure 10 illustrates the prediction performance using zero-shot test data from Google Cells G and H. OmniFORE achieves an MAE of 1.22×10^{-3} , RMSE of 6.74×10^{-3} , and SMAPE of 4.28%. ModernTCN follows closely with an MAE of 1.51×10^{-3} , RMSE of 7.53×10^{-3} , and SMAPE of 4.37%. In comparison, AGCRN records an MAE of 1.59×10^{-2} , RMSE of 3.19×10^{-2} , and SMAPE of 111.07%, while LSTNet shows an MAE of 5.17×10^{-3} , RMSE of 1.34×10^{-2} , and SMAPE of 28.37%.

OmniFORE’s superior zero-shot performance demonstrates its robust generalization capabilities, outperforming ModernTCN by 19.35%, AGCRN by 92.32%, and LSTNet by 76.44% in MAE. In contrast, AGCRN and LSTNet perform worse on zero-shot data, indicating potential benefits from information leakage between training and test sets. Additionally, data variability and the exact nature of loaded traces can influence performance outcomes.

FIGURE 11. Generalization performance comparison of MAE, RMSE, and SMAPE for each model on the cross-dataset Alibaba traces.

c: Cross-Dataset Generalization

To evaluate transferability across heterogeneous cloud environments, we test models on the Alibaba 2022 microservices trace dataset [55] without retraining. This represents an extreme generalization scenario where models must adapt to significantly different workload distributions. We process pod MS_11349 data by down-sampling from 1-minute to 5-minute intervals to match the Google traces’ sampling rate.

OmniFORE demonstrates strong transfer learning capabilities with an MAE of 7.27×10^{-3} , outperforming ModernTCN by 30.41%, AGCRN by 74.67%, and LSTNet by 84.70%. This significant performance gap highlights OmniFORE’s ability to extract fundamental workload patterns that transcend dataset-specific characteristics, making it particularly valuable for deployment across diverse cloud environments.

4) Impact of Prediction Length on Inference Time

In the millisecond regime, longer prediction lengths are particularly advantageous [57]. Short-term predictions require frequent adjustments, leading to higher computational overhead and inefficiencies. In contrast, longer-term predictions enhance stability and responsiveness, allowing for smoother and more strategic resource management. This reduces the need for constant real-time recalibration and optimizes overall performance in edge-cloud environments.

As shown in Figure 12, we study the inference time (left subplot) and the performance in terms of RMSE (right subplot) over different prediction lengths. The inference time subplot reveals that LSTNet’s computation time significantly increases with prediction length, reaching 240 ms for a length of 300, making it unsuitable for real-time applications that require latency within the 50 ms limit [58]. In contrast, OmniFORE maintains low inference times, from 12.7 ms for a length of 5 to 34 ms for 300, thanks to efficient attention mechanisms and fast decoding. AGCRN’s inference time also rises

FIGURE 12. Impact of prediction length on inference time and RMSE for OmniFORE, AGCRN, LSTNet, and ModernTCN.

with longer predictions, reaching 56 ms for 300, which exceeds the real-time requirement, but remains higher than OmniFORE. Notably, ModernTCN demonstrates remarkably low inference times in the microsecond range (approximately 6 μ s across all prediction lengths), which is orders of magnitude faster than the other models. This exceptional speed is achieved through ModernTCN’s pure convolution-based architecture with linear complexity, avoiding the computational overhead of attention mechanisms used in transformer-based models. Overall, OmniFORE is approximately twice as fast as AGCRN across all prediction lengths while maintaining performance, as evidenced by the RMSE results in the right subplot.

OmniFORE consistently outperforms AGCRN and LSTNet in RMSE, demonstrating superior accuracy. AGCRN’s RMSE is generally low performant. While ModernTCN delivers exceptional computational efficiency, its RMSE values show lower prediction accuracy than OmniFORE. This accuracy trade-off highlights that ModernTCN’s simpler architecture, while faster, captures fewer complex temporal dependencies. OmniFORE’s combination of low inference time and high accuracy makes it ideal for real-time, dynamic applications, outperforming both AGCRN and LSTNet while offering a better balance between speed and accuracy than ModernTCN.

5) Periodic Dynamic Workload Changes with Long-term Dependencies

To rigorously test OmniFORE’s attention mechanism and its capacity to capture long-range dependencies, we design a signal with frequent, highly dynamic changes based on the workload diversity described in Section III (Figure 13). The signal’s periodic nature, alternating between low and high usage over extended cycles, challenges the model to recognize and utilize information from distant time steps, rigorously evaluating its long-term pattern recognition capabilities.

The workload components are defined as

$$T(t) = \mu (\sin(2\pi ft) \cdot \mathbf{1}_{\{t\%(1/f) < 0.5\}} + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma)), \quad (32)$$

where μ represents the mean value for the workload, f is the frequency, and σ is the standard deviation. The indicator function $\mathbf{1}_{\{t\%(1/f)<0.5\}}$ ensures that the sine wave is active for half of its period. $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma)$ represents Gaussian noise with a mean of 0 and standard deviation σ . The overall workload signal is generated by combining a low and high workload component:

$$T(t) = \begin{cases} T_{\text{low}}(t), & \text{if } t < \text{pattern_length}/2 \\ T_{\text{high}}(t), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

where $\text{pattern_length} = 48$, representing a 2-hour cycle with 5-minute intervals. For the low workload component, $\mu_{\text{low}} = 0.01$, $f_{\text{low}} = 0.5$, and $\sigma_{\text{low}} = 0.002$. For the high workload component, $\mu_{\text{high}} = 0.08$, $f_{\text{high}} = 1.0$, and $\sigma_{\text{high}} = 0.01$. The final workload is then adjusted to ensure positive values:

$$T_{\text{final}}(t) = T(t) + \mu_{\text{low}}. \quad (34)$$

The connection between these equations and the input sequence lengths (d_x) lies in the periodic nature of the generated data. Each data point represents a 5-minute interval, making the input sequence lengths for OmniFORE (98 intervals), ModernTCN (184 intervals), AGCRN (48 intervals), and LSTNet (161 intervals) (see Table 1), adequate to capture the recurring patterns of the workload cycles.

Analysis of OmniFORE, ModernTCN, AGCRN, and LSTNet reveals that OmniFORE consistently outperforms the other models. OmniFORE achieves an RMSE of 0.0322, ModernTCN, 0.0380 for AGCRN and 0.0806 for LSTNet. The lower RMSE indicates that OmniFORE's predictions have smaller average deviations from the true values, demonstrating its superior accuracy in capturing the dynamic workload patterns.

OmniFORE's advanced attention mechanism demonstrates a superior ability to understand long-term dependencies, enabling it to accurately predict dynamic changes in the workload. This capability is evident in its precise anticipation of transitions between low and high workload periods. In contrast, ModernTCN, AGCRN and LSTNet exhibit limitations in capturing these long-range patterns, resulting in greater deviations from the true values, particularly during workload transitions. LSTNet's performance is hindered by its inability to effectively model dependencies beyond approximately 40 data points, a consequence of the vanishing gradient problem [33]. Similarly, the CNN-based approach employed by ModernTCN and AGCRN struggles with long-range dependencies [16], [18], impeding its ability to accurately capture and predict extended periodic patterns in the workload signal.

Notably, even in the low workload regions of the signal, OmniFORE demonstrates an understanding of the existence of minor peaks, showcasing its ability to capture fine-grained patterns in the data.

FIGURE 13. Comparison of true and predicted values for OmniFORE, AGCRN, and LSTNet under dynamic workload changes.

FIGURE 14. Comparison of true and zero-shot predicted values for OmniFORE, ModernTCN, AGCRN, and LSTNet on a regular training dataset.

6) Variance-based Performance Analysis

We compare OmniFORE, ModernTCN, AGCRN, and LSTNet models on both the regular CPU cores dataset and the zero-shot dataset introduced in Section 3 to assess their capacity to handle data with heterogeneous variance levels (Figure 14). OmniFORE demonstrates superior performance in capturing both low and high variance patterns, evidenced by its closer alignment with true values across diverse trace volatilities. This advantage is particularly pronounced in highly fluctuating traces, where OmniFORE maintains accuracy while ModernTCN, AGCRN and LSTNet show increased deviations. The consistent performance of OmniFORE across both datasets underscores its robust generalization capabilities, effectively adapting to previously unseen patterns in the zero-shot scenario.

To further investigate, we measured the variance of each individual test trace $T_{\text{val},i}$ and computed the performance metrics (MAE and RMSE) for these traces. Figure 15 shows the relationship between trace variance and performance metrics, with linear trend lines fitted to highlight trends.

FIGURE 15. Trace variance vs. MAE and RMSE for OmniFORE, ModernTCN, AGCRN, and LSTNet models, with fitted linear lines.

In Figure 15, slopes indicate error increase rates with rising input variance. OmniFORE exhibits the lowest slopes (regular: 1.51×10^1 , zero-shot: 1.58×10^0), outperforming ModernTCN (regular: 1.73×10^1 , zero-shot: 1.96×10^0), AGCRN (regular: 1.76×10^1 , zero-shot: -2.22×10^1) and LSTNet (regular: 2.45×10^1 , zero-shot: 8.80×10^0). This demonstrates OmniFORE’s superior robustness to high-variance data, particularly in zero-shot scenarios.

We evaluate OmniFORE, ModernTCN, AGCRN, and LSTNet on low and high variance traces in both regular and zero-shot scenarios. For the five lowest variance traces, OmniFORE-regular achieves an MAE of 1.34×10^{-6} , outperforming AGCRN-regular (5.27×10^{-5}) and LSTNet-regular (1.79×10^{-6}) by 97.5% and 25.1% respectively. ModernTCN-regular achieves an MAE of 1.20×10^{-6} , performing slightly better than OmniFORE. On high variance traces, OmniFORE-regular (MAE: 7.73×10^{-3}) surpasses ModernTCN-regular (8.69×10^{-3}) by 11.0%, AGCRN-regular (8.98×10^{-3}) by 13.9% and LSTNet-regular (1.18×10^{-2}) by 34.5%. In the zero-shot scenario with high variance traces, OmniFORE (MAE: 2.05×10^{-3}) outperforms ModernTCN (2.56×10^{-3}) by 19.9%, AGCRN (4.12×10^{-3}) and LSTNet (1.16×10^{-2}) by 50.2% and 82.3% respectively. These results demonstrate OmniFORE’s consistent superiority across diverse variance levels and generalization scenarios.

7) Convergence

Quick model convergence is crucial to reduce the need for extensive training, which aids in deploying updates and maintaining overall system performance. Additionally, models that converge faster are less prone to overfitting, as they achieve their optimal state in fewer epochs.

Figure 16 depicts the test RMSE convergence of OmniFORE, ModernTCN, AGCRN, and LSTNet models over multiple epochs, with early stopping applied.

FIGURE 16. Convergence of OmniFORE, ModernTCN, AGCRN, and LSTNet models over epochs.

OmniFORE demonstrates the fastest convergence, achieving the lowest RMSE of 3.29×10^{-3} by the 7th epoch. ModernTCN follows with 3.81×10^{-3} by the 13th epoch. AGCRN exhibits slower convergence, reaching 4.61×10^{-3} by the 15th epoch. LSTNet converges more quickly but with higher error, reaching 4.75×10^{-3} by the 5th epoch.

8) Temporal Workload Clustering Analysis

This section examines our temporal clustering approach, a key component of OmniFORE’s generalization capabilities. We introduce metrics for quantifying clustering quality, analyze CNN hyperparameter effects on pattern recognition, demonstrate latent space effectiveness through visualization, and validate cluster stability. These analyses confirm that our method extracts genuine workload patterns, contributing directly to forecasting performance.

a: Clustering Metrics

We evaluate clustering quality using four complementary metrics:

- **Silhouette Score** [59]: Measures cluster cohesion and separation (-1 to 1, higher is better):

$$s(i) = \frac{b(i) - a(i)}{\max\{a(i), b(i)\}} \quad (35)$$

where $s(i)$ is the silhouette coefficient for the i -th data point, $a(i)$ is the mean distance between the i -th point and all other points in the same cluster, and $b(i)$ is the mean distance between the i -th point and all points in the nearest neighboring cluster. The overall silhouette score is the average of $s(i)$ over all data points.

- **Davies-Bouldin Index** [60]: Evaluates cluster separation (lower is better):

$$DB = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K \max_{j \neq i} \left(\frac{\sigma_i + \sigma_j}{d(c_i, c_j)} \right) \quad (36)$$

where K is the number of clusters, σ_i is the average distance of all points in cluster i to the cluster centroid c_i , and $d(c_i, c_j)$ is the distance between centroids of clusters i and j .

- **Calinski-Harabasz Index** [61]: Measures the ratio of between-cluster to within-cluster variance (higher is better):

$$CH = \frac{SS_B}{SS_W} \times \frac{N_{\text{cluster}} - K}{K - 1} \quad (37)$$

where SS_B is the between-cluster variance (sum of squares), SS_W is the within-cluster variance, N_{cluster} is the total number of data points in the clustering analysis, and K is the number of clusters. Note that N_{cluster} represents the number of temporal segments extracted from the original traces $\{T_i\}_{i=1}^{N_{\text{all}}}$.

- **Normalized Mutual Information** [62]: Measures clustering consistency (0 to 1):

$$NMI(U, V) = \frac{2 \times I(U, V)}{H(U) + H(V)} \quad (38)$$

where U and V represent two different cluster assignments (e.g., from different runs or algorithms), $I(U, V)$ is the mutual information between these assignments, and $H(U)$ and $H(V)$ are the entropies of the respective cluster assignments. This metric evaluates the stability of clustering results across different runs.

b: CNN Hyperparameter Impact on Clustering Quality

We study how CNN hyperparameters affect clustering performance using a parameter grid of kernel sizes (3-9) and filter counts (16-128). Figure 17 shows the silhouette score results.

Our analysis reveals three important findings. First, optimal parameter selection improves clustering quality by 33.2%. Second, filter count influences clustering quality 2.5× more than kernel size. Third, the parameters interact in a non-linear manner. The optimal configuration (kernel=7, filters=128) significantly improves zero-shot generalization by capturing meaningful temporal patterns.

c: Latent Space Effectiveness via t-SNE Visualization

Figure 18 compares t-SNE visualizations of raw time series versus our learned latent representations. The latent space improves silhouette score by 131.8% (0.178 to 0.413) and inter-cluster distance by 50.3%, while reducing dimensionality by 98.6%. This visualization confirms our model transforms complex temporal patterns into well-separated clusters without requiring prior pattern knowledge.

FIGURE 17. CNN hyperparameter effects on clustering quality showing silhouette scores across different configurations, with the optimal configuration (kernel=7, filters=128) achieving a score of 0.553.

FIGURE 18. t-SNE visualization: original time series (left) versus latent representation (right), showing improved cluster separation (131.8% higher silhouette score).

d: Cluster Stability and Optimal Cluster Count

To address the sensitivity of the initialization of K-means, we performed 100 clustering runs with different random seeds. The results show exceptional stability: mean NMI of 0.960, minimal variation of the silhouette score (0.562 ± 0.003), and 98.9% of points that maintain consistent cluster assignments across runs. This stability analysis confirms that our clusters represent genuine workload patterns, rather than initialization artifacts. We determined the optimal cluster count ($k=11$) using a consensus of four metrics: Elbow Method, Silhouette Score, Davies-Bouldin Index, and Calinski-Harabasz Index.

e: Impact of Clustering vs Random Sampling on Prediction Generalization

To directly isolate the effect of our clustering-based trace selection (see Section IV., S_1-S_5 and Figure 19), we compared two approaches for selecting training data: training on 100 clustered traces versus 100 randomly

FIGURE 19. Generalization benefit of clustering-based trace selection over random sampling: clustering yields substantially lower MAE, RMSE, and SMAPE on zero-shot workloads.

sampled traces (five runs averaged), using the regular set (Google Cells A–F) for training and the zero-shot set (Cells G and H; see Section 2 and Section b) for evaluation. Specifically, we trained one informer model using the 100 traces selected by our clustering method, and five separate informer models using five different random subsets of 100 traces each. For each random subset, a new Informer model was independently trained, so that all models are of the same architecture and only differ in their training data. The random selection is repeated five times to obtain an average performance and ensure more trustworthy, robust results.

Clustering-based selection led to much better generalization: compared to random sampling, MAE was reduced by 20.66%, RMSE by 24.63%, and SMAPE by 32.71%. Figure 19 compares these metrics for both methods, demonstrating that clustering results in more representative training sets and improved zero-shot performance.

C. Deployment Considerations

While our evaluation demonstrates OmniFORE’s forecasting capabilities in controlled environments, practical deployment in edge-cloud systems requires additional considerations. OmniFORE’s flexible architecture supports both centralized and distributed deployment strategies, allowing practitioners to select the approach that best fits their application needs. Centralized deployment maximizes generalization by enabling a single model to serve diverse workloads, reducing the overhead of managing multiple models, but may increase communication delays. In contrast, distributed deployment places models closer to the edge, minimizing latency but requiring multiple models and potentially reducing generalization. The choice of deployment thus depends on the desired balance between generalization capability and communication efficiency [63]. For empirical measurements of edge, fog, and cloud API response times, we refer readers to existing literature. Based on the performance characteristics observed in Section V.B, we

propose potential deployment approaches for real-world implementations.

A promising strategy involves adopting a centralized “master model” architecture, where OmniFORE operates primarily on cloud infrastructure and serves predictions to edge devices through lightweight API calls [58], [64]. This approach would leverage OmniFORE’s efficient inference capabilities while addressing the resource constraints typical of edge environments [10]. The master model could collect workload data from multiple edge nodes, potentially improving forecast quality through more general pattern recognition across the network [25].

The low inference times demonstrated by OmniFORE in our evaluation suggest that it could theoretically support multiple concurrent edge devices with timely predictions. The minimal processing overhead of OmniFORE is particularly crucial in a centralized deployment architecture, as it helps offset the inherent network delays associated with remote model access, thus keeping the total response latency within acceptable limits for resource allocation decisions [65], [66]. However, actual deployment would need to address several practical challenges, including intermittent connectivity in edge environments [10], consistent versioning of the model across heterogeneous infrastructure [65], and adaptation to diverse hardware capabilities at different network levels [66].

Integration with existing container orchestration frameworks represents another potential implementation pathway [67]. Orchestration systems could potentially use OmniFORE’s predictions to proactively allocate resources based on anticipated workload changes [2]. The model’s demonstrated ability to handle high-variance workloads suggests that it might be particularly valuable for managing dynamic resource requirements in containerized environments [2], [10].

Future work should include real-world deployment studies to validate these approaches in production environments, measure actual system performance improvements, and identify practical implementation challenges beyond those observed in our controlled evaluation environment [10], [25].

CONCLUSION

This paper has introduced OmniFORE, a novel framework for optimizing resource forecasts in edge-cloud networks. By integrating the innovative components of the OmniFORE framework, including attention-based time-series modeling, temporal clustering, strategic data sampling, and advanced generalization techniques, OmniFORE achieves robust generalization and efficiently predicts diverse workloads in volatile environments. Our approach leverages strategic data sampling to extract representative traces, employs temporal clustering to differentiate workload patterns, and utilizes advanced

attention mechanisms to capture both short-term and long-term dependencies. Extensive experiments on real-world datasets demonstrated that OmniFORE consistently outperforms existing benchmark schemes across various scenarios, including regular and zero-shot predictions. The framework showed significant improvements in prediction accuracy, inference speed, and adaptability to both low and high variance data. These advancements mark a substantial step forward in addressing the complexities of cloud-native workloads, paving the way for more adaptive and responsive edge-cloud systems. Future work could explore the application of OmniFORE to other domains requiring accurate time-series forecasting and investigate its potential for enhancing real-time decision-making in dynamic computing environments.

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